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4 **Supplementary material: Principal component analysis** 5 **of the 2010 reversal of core-surface flow beneath the** 6 **Pacific Ocean**

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16 **S1 Analysis of flow model performance**

17 This supplementary section provides a bit more detail about the different flow models' ability to fit the data, and the
18 power spectra for each flow model.

19 Figure S1.1 shows observed SV at three ground observatories – Eskdalemuir, Guam, and Eyrewell, and at three
20 nearby GVOs. The shifts up and down the y-axis for each of the GVOs is because of the altitude differences of their
21 corresponding satellites. The satellite data quality is variable, with those from Ørsted and Cryosat-2 noisier than from
22 CHAMP, and with the Swarm data yielding the cleanest signal. Figure S1.1 also shows the SV predictions from each
23 of the three models. The three model predictions are very similar, and can be difficult to distinguish, as would be
24 expected from their similar rms misfits. We see from each of the models that they are largely in good agreement with
25 the data. The only exception to this is the SA flow predictions in the Pacific after 2010, where there is a systematic
26 difference between the SA and the other models. This is particularly evident in \dot{B}_ϕ at Guam (Figure S1.1c), and \dot{B}_r
27 at Eyrewell (Figure S1.1e). Where the data are noisier, for example between 2012 and 2013, before the availability
28 of the Swarm data, there is slightly more variation in the model predictions. This is particularly clear in the radial
29 component at Eyrewell in Figure S1.1e.

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(a) Eskdalemuir observatory(55.1°N, 3.2°W)

(b) GVO near Eskdalemuir (53.5°N, 3.0°W)

(c) Guam observatory (13.5°N, 144.9°E)

Figure S1.1: SV data and model predictions at Eskdalemuir, Guam, and Eyrewell observatories, and 3 nearby virtual observatories. Error bars are 1 standard deviation.

(d) GVO near Guam (6.0°N , 164.4°E)

(e) Eyrewell (43.2°S , 172.4°E)

(f) GVO near Eyrewell (41.8°S , 173.4°E)

Figure S1.1: Continued

(a) Minimum acceleration

(b) TO-like

(c) SA

Figure S1.2: Power spectrum of toroidal (left) and poloidal (right) flow components for each model type, up to $L_u = 14$, as a function of time and spherical harmonic (SH) degree. Values above $L_u = 14$ are negligibly small, and thus not shown here. The colour indicates velocity power, as given by the z-axis. Note that the z-axes scales differ.

Figure S1.3: Power spectrum of toroidal (left) and poloidal (right) flow components for each model type, as a function of time and spherical harmonic (SH) degree. It is the same spectra as Figure S1.2, but projected differently. Note that the y-axes scales differ.

Table S2.1: Model parameters for minimum acceleration, TO-like, and SA models.

		Minimum acceleration	TO-like	SA
Spatial damping	λ_v^{symm}	5×10^{-4}	5×10^{-4}	10^{-4}
	λ_v^{asymm}	5×10^{-4}	5×10^{-4}	5×10^{-3}
Temporal damping	λ_t^{zt}	10^3	1	10^3
	λ_t^{nzt}	10^3	1×10^3	10^3
Normalised r.m.s. misfit		1.60	1.60	1.61
Spatial norm value ($\text{km}^{-2}\text{yr}^{-2}$)		4.22×10^7	4.21×10^7	1.41×10^8

30 Figure S1.2 and S1.3 shows the power spectra separately for the toroidal and poloidal flow components for each
31 model type. For toroidal flow in the minimum acceleration and TO-like flows, the flow was dominated by degree 1
32 until 2010, where degree 2 takes over, marking the change from eastward to westward flow in the Pacific. These flow
33 components continue to decrease and increase in power, for degrees 1 and 2, respectively, from the beginning of the
34 model until around 2020, where degree 1 plateaus for the minimum acceleration flow and rises for the TO-like flow,
35 and degree 2 decreases in power for both models. Poloidal flow is 10% the strength of the toroidal flow, and there
36 is a rise in degree 3 after 2010, which has doubled in power by 2025. This represents the equatorial Pacific up- and
37 downwelling shown in Figure 2, (see Figure S2.11 for spectra associated with the Pacific overturn). For the SA flow,
38 we see a similar trend for the toroidal coefficients, but the toroidal degree 2 components do not become dominant until
39 2018. This flow is dominated by the toroidal flow, with the poloidal flow components half the power of their TO-like
40 and minimum acceleration counterparts. However, whereas the other two flows have a gradual decrease in power with
41 increasing toroidal flow degree, the SA flow has higher energy in spherical harmonic degrees 5–10.

42 S2 Supplementary tables and figures

43 This section provides supplementary tables and figures to the main paper.

Figure S2.1: Similar to Figure 4, but comparing PCs from minimum acceleration model, with and without normalising the flow coefficient to homogeneous kinetic energy (KE-norm). Figure shows temporal variance of PC1–10, separately for toroidal and poloidal coefficients, and the difference between cumulative variance, for normalised and unnormalised coefficients.

Figure S2.2: Average azimuthal velocity around the tangent cylinder (latitudes $\pm 68^\circ$, -72°), in the region under the Bering strait where the planetary gyre touches the tangent cylinder, and its counterpart in the southern hemisphere (longitudes 150°E , -150°W). The shaded area corresponds to $\pm 1\sigma$ within the region over which the average is evaluated.

Figure S2.3: Singular spectra for minimum acceleration, TO-like, and SA flow models. Errors are estimated by North’s rule of thumb (North et al., 1982; Domingos et al., 2019), and degenerate values are identified from values whose eigenvalue decrease less than the associated error of its neighbour (see equation B2 in Pais et al., 2015). TO-like and SA spectra are vertically shifted by a magnitude of 10 and 100, respectively, for clarity. Noise plateau is estimated from linear best fit to values after the 20th eigenvalue.

Figure S2.4: The first 9 principal components (PCs) of the TO-like flow, and snapshots of those flows in 2007 and 2020. The PC time-series has times of geomagnetic jerks in the 21st century marked in grey, and the times of the flow snapshots marked in red. Flow is superimposed on poloidal flow potential, S , where $S > 0$ is indicative of fluid upwelling, and $S < 0$ is indicative of downwelling. Plots are in Robinson projection, centred on 180° longitude, and continents are shown for reference only. Note that flow and flow potential colour scales change with each plot.

Figure S2.4: Continued

Figure S2.5: The first 9 principal components (PCs) of the SA flow, and snapshots of those flows in 2007 and 2020. The PC time-series has times of geomagnetic jerks in the 21st century marked in grey, and the times of the flow snapshots marked in red. Flow is superimposed on poloidal flow potential, S , where $S > 0$ is indicative of fluid upwelling, and $S < 0$ is indicative of downwelling. Plots are in Robinson projection, centred on 180° longitude, and continents are shown for reference only. Note that flow and flow potential colour scales change with each plot.

Figure S2.5: Continued

Figure S2.6: Similar to Figure 4, but for separate PCA of toroidal and poloidal flow coefficients. Figure shows temporal variance of PC1–10, separately for toroidal and poloidal coefficients, and the cumulative variance, for all three flows. Dashed horizontal lines show 99% and 99.9% variance.

Figure S2.7: Same as Figure 5, but for separate PCA for toroidal and poloidal coefficients.

Figure S2.7: Continued

Figure S2.8: Same as Figure S2.4, but for separate PCA of toroidal and poloidal coefficients.

Figure S2.8: Continued

Figure S2.9: Same as Figure S2.5, but for separate PCA of toroidal and poloidal coefficients.

Figure S2.9: Continued

Figure S2.10: Same as Figure 5, but for PCs 7–9.

Figure S2.11: Power spectrum of toroidal (left) and poloidal (right) flow coefficients for principal components (PCs) 1 and 2 for the minimum acceleration model, as a function of time and spherical harmonic (SH) degree. Values above $L_u = 14$ are negligibly small, and thus not shown here. The colour indicates velocity power, as given by the z-axis. Note that the z-axis scales differ.

Figure S2.12: Power spectrum of toroidal (left) and poloidal (right) flow coefficients for principal components (PCs) 1 and 2 for the minimum acceleration model, as a function of time and spherical harmonic (SH) degree. It is the same spectra as in Figure S2.11, projected differently.

Figure S2.13: Advected SV at Swarm altitude ($c = 6861.20$ km) at the three GVOs shown in Figure S1.1, from PC1–2 (blue), PC3–9 (red), and their sum (PC1–9, orange), for all three models, and compared to CHAOS-8.3 (Kloss et al., 2025) (purple). Timings of geomagnetic jerks (1999: Manda et al. (2000) ; 2003: Wardinski et al. (2008) ; 2007: Chulliat et al. (2010) ; 2011: Chulliat and Maus (2014) ; 2014: Torta et al. (2015) ; 2017: Whaler et al. (2022) ; 2020: Pavón-Carrasco et al. (2021) ; 2024: Madsen et al. (2025)) are shaded in grey.

Figure S2.14: Same as Figure 7, but for separate PCA of toroidal and poloidal coefficients.